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ABSTRACT

Why are some citizens satisfied with democracy while others are not? The reasons are multiple and categorically different, ranging from their satisfaction in life, job, family incomes and the environment they live in, to the assessment of economic performance of the country they live in, to their public experiences with institutions, and the level of trust in them. This article approaches the issue from a different perspective, an “internal”, or if you will, a slightly more “endogenous” one. It argues that satisfaction with democracy depends not only on detailed aspects of evaluations with democratic performance but also on whether democracy meets citizens’ normative expectations regarding what democracy should be, what are the constitutive components of democracy. Using data from the European Social Survey democracy modules (2012 and 2022), the study examines how these normative expectations, performance evaluations, and expectation–performance gaps across multiple democratic dimensions shape satisfaction with democracy across European regions and age groups. The results show that larger expectation–performance gaps consistently reduce satisfaction with democracy across democratic aspects and dimensions. While positive performance evaluations remain the strongest predictor of democratic satisfaction, normative expectations exert a conditional effect: expectations increase satisfaction when democratic performance is perceived as strong but reduce satisfaction when performance falls short. The findings also reveal significant generational differences. Younger Europeans place greater emphasis on minority rights and redistributive outcomes, whereas older citizens’ satisfaction depends more strongly on institutional guarantees such as elections and rule of law. Finally, the importance of unmet social-democratic expectations appears to have been particularly pronounced in the aftermath of the Great Recession, especially in Southern Europe and among younger cohorts.

1. Introduction

This study aims to analyze how contemporary Europeans' preferences for democracy and their evaluations of democratic performance affect their satisfaction with democracy. We seek to determine the extent to which young Europeans differ from older and oldest cohorts on these dimensions, whether systematic regional patterns are observable, and whether there have been meaningful shifts over the past decade and a half. More broadly, we aim to address the question of whether it is possible to speak of a universal European youth, or whether the differences across the continent are substantial enough to reject such a conclusion. The article adopts a conventional approach in contemporary comparative political science: it provides an empirical test of theoretical claims and hypotheses advanced in a rapidly expanding literature on democratic quality, competing normative conceptions of democracy, the determinants of democratic preferences, satisfaction with democracy, and the challenges confronting contemporary democratic theory (Ferrin & Kriesi 2016; 2025; Levitsky & Ziblatt 2018; Achen & Bartels 2017; Bartels 2023; Haggard & Kaufman 2021; Przeworski 2019).

The analysis shows that satisfaction with democracy in Europe is shaped not only by how citizens evaluate democratic performance but also by how these evaluations match their normative expectations of what democracy should be, what are the definitional elements of contemporary democracies. Using data from the European Social Survey (2012–2022), we demonstrate that larger expectation–performance gaps systematically reduce democratic satisfaction across institutional dimensions. While positive performance evaluations remain the strongest predictors of satisfaction with democracy, normative expectations play an important conditional role: expectations increase satisfaction when democratic performance is perceived as strong but depress it when performance is judged insufficient. The results also reveal important generational and temporal differences. Younger citizens tend to place greater weight on minority rights and redistributive outcomes when evaluating democracy, whereas older citizens' satisfaction depends more strongly on institutional guarantees such as elections and rule of law. Moreover, the importance of

social-democratic expectations appears to have been particularly pronounced in the aftermath of the Great Recession, when unmet expectations regarding redistribution and social protection were more strongly associated with dissatisfaction with democracy, especially in Southern Europe and among younger and middle-aged citizens.

These findings suggest that democratic legitimacy in Europe increasingly depends on whether democratic institutions meet evolving generational expectations. Persistent expectation–performance gaps in key democratic dimensions may therefore represent an underappreciated source of democratic dissatisfaction and potential instability.

2. Theoretical Foundation

Let us begin with a “technical” observation. Although we have access to a substantial body of research on the contemporary condition of Europe’s youth and on young people’s political attitudes - including attitudes toward democracy - there remains a notable shortage of studies that rigorously test intergenerational differences while explicitly modelling temporal change and systematically comparing individual countries and European regions. For this reason, the theoretical discussion that follows is necessarily selective and focuses only on contributions that directly address the core questions examined in this article. As a further consequence, the field still lacks robust and broadly convincing theoretical generalizations. Despite these limitations, we nonetheless possess several well-grounded insights into young Europeans’ orientations toward democracy.

One key contribution of recent scholarship is the reframing of the “youth question” as an issue of political inequality within youth cohorts, rather than a uniform generational shift. Using comparative data from nine European countries, Grasso and Giugni (2021) document pronounced social-class disparities in young people’s political participation and engagement. This perspective helps explain why aggregate indicators may appear stable even as democracy-related frustrations intensify in specific segments of young adulthood (e.g., economically insecure renters, precarious workers, and those outside higher education). It also aligns with policy-oriented qualitative research showing that disadvantaged young people often experience politics as distant and ineffective, weakening

perceived democratic relevance even when abstract support for democracy remains high (Cohen et al. 2024).

A second strand of recent scholarship examines support for alternatives to party-parliamentary representation. Existing work has developed increasingly nuanced mappings of these preferences, distinguishing not only between anti-liberal orientations (e.g. support for strong leaders unconstrained by institutions) and technocratic preferences for expert-led decision-making, but also a broader range of participatory and deliberative models, including citizens' assemblies, sortition, and other forms of direct involvement. Research on technocratic and authoritarian alternatives (Russo et al. 2025) demonstrates that anti-party sentiment can map onto different regime visions - expert rule versus unconstrained executive power - with distinct predictors and consequences. Deliberative democracy, meanwhile, has become a key reference point in debates on democratic renewal. Cross-national evidence from 15 Western European countries indicates that support for sortition-based citizens' assemblies is often higher among citizens with lower political competence and anti-elite sentiment, and is partly conditional on expected outcomes. In the youth-democracy context, this matters because young adults may be skeptical of parties yet supportive of participation-enhancing reforms - stances that may appear "anti-system" in older frameworks but are better interpreted as demands for responsiveness or institutional substitution (Pilet et al. 2023). Recent research shows that, when addressing these demands, democratic innovations (for a thorough review, see Gaiba et al. [2025]), should move beyond isolated participatory experiments toward the construction of coherent participatory ecosystems that reduce participation costs while increase its political effectiveness (Moskovic et al. 2026).

A further recent trend is to treat democratic attitudes as multi-level: young Europeans form distinct evaluations of national democracy and EU governance, and these assessments do not always move in tandem. European Parliament youth surveys track perceived influence, policy priorities, and evaluations of EU responsiveness and democratic quality, consistently revealing a gap between support for the European project and frustration with perceived bureaucratic distance or ineffectiveness (Cella & Monasterio 2025)

This is conceptually important for research on 18–35-year-olds because EU-level politics often shapes young adults' lives through mobility, education, labor markets, and rights, while accountability remains harder to identify. Youth attitudes therefore increasingly

feature “institutional mismatch” claims: democratic ideals are endorsed, but governance is experienced as too remote, too slow, or elite-captured. These perceptions can underpin either pro-reform orientations (e.g., deliberative and participatory channels) or anti-system trajectories (e.g., withdrawal or populist hostility).

Across recent scholarship, one publication-ready conclusion stands out: “*Do not equate democratic dissatisfaction with democratic rejection*”. Young adults frequently report low trust and low satisfaction, yet their support for democratic principles often remains resilient. The key analytical task is to identify when dissatisfaction shifts into regime skepticism, and through which mechanisms – political efficacy, exclusion, perceived unfairness. Recent cross-European evidence (nine countries) finds that the youngest adults are no less supportive of liberal democracy than older cohorts; moreover, while anti-democratic attitudes reduce mobilization, this relationship is not age-specific—critical views rarely translate into democratic apathy among youth. The research shows moreover how young people’s individual traits are likely to mature into different value patterns of democratic engagement over time but within specific contexts (Fernandez Guzman Grassi 2023). These findings align well with studies that convincingly emphasize the importance of “critical citizens” or “dissatisfied democrats” for the quality of democracy (Norris 1999; Klingemann 1999).

Our study seeks to address a set of more specific questions that have indeed surfaced in some existing work by fellow scholars, but either were not pursued with comparable granularity, or did not foreground the intergenerational dimension, or did not incorporate a temporal perspective. Rigorous research designs capable of systematically examining these relationships - and of providing clear answers to these (for now broadly formulated) questions - remain relatively scarce. There is little doubt, however, that the European Social Survey (ESS) offers precisely such a basis for analysis, especially through the so-called “democracy modules” included in Round 6 (2012) and Round 10 (2022). These modules contain several dozen items and variables pertaining to democracy and are, to a substantial extent, directly comparable across waves.

Crucially, what matters is not only the availability of these measures, but also the overarching conceptual architecture of the project (for details, see Ferrin & Kriesi 2016: 1–22), which advocates moving beyond several research traditions that have long dominated the study of democratic attitudes. First, it argues that it is insufficient to focus solely on a general, abstract preference for democracy as a political system and an equally general

“overall” assessment of democracy’s performance. Instead, researchers should examine attitudes toward specific democratic attributes, such as judicial independence, media autonomy, availability of referenda, political accountability, among others. Second, the framework rejects the assumption of a single, unitary model of democracy. Rather, it proceeds from the premise that multiple, competing models coexist—corresponding to distinct traditions present in democratic theory, including procedural-elitist conceptions (Weber, Schumpeter), direct or participatory/self-government traditions (Marx), pluralist models (Dahl), and the like (see Held 1987). Third, it explicitly recognizes that countries and regions within Europe exhibit distinctive patterns, both in terms of the level of support for particular normative elements of democracy and in terms of evaluations of how well those elements function in practice; moreover, this specificity often pertains to particular democratic attributes rather than to democracy “in general.” Fourth, it posits that satisfaction with specific democratic attributes is shaped by normative expectations concerning those attributes and the weight individuals assign to them, while also allowing for a reverse mechanism: higher or lower expectations regarding a given democratic component may itself be conditioned by the perceived extent to which that component is accomplished and thus by experienced satisfaction. Evidence consistent with these expectations was already reported in detailed analyses of the 2012 Round 6 module (Torcal & Trechsel 2016: 231–232).

Against this backdrop, it is useful to recall several salient findings from analyses of both democracy modules.

Shifting focus to attitudes towards democracy of Europeans as a whole, without distinguishing by age, let us begin with a few fundamental aspects. As emphasized already, the essence of the ESS study was not limited to posing general questions about democracy – whether it is considered a desirable system and how its functioning is assessed in particular countries. Rather, the study examined multiple concrete dimensions and aspects (elements) of democracy from two perspectives: detailed **normative expectations** regarding multiple aspects of democracy and **evaluations of their actual functioning** – the performance of those aspects in particular countries (Ferrin, Kriesi 2025).

These specific democratic aspects – approached in an identical form for both the normative (what democracy *should* entail) and evaluative (how democracy performs – *how it works in practice*) dimensions - were carefully selected on the basis of theoretical scholarship and earlier landmark empirical studies (Almond & Verba 1963; Conovan 1999;

Kirsch & Welzel 2019; Mair 2009; Mudde & Kaltwasser 2017). Beyond the most self-evident set of attributes that constitute the ontological core of the liberal-democratic model, the ESS framework also captures elements associated with a social-democratic (redistributive) conception of democracy as well as a direct-democratic model. In addition, the 2022 module incorporates - though only for that wave - items tapping a populist model of democracy (Mair 2009; Urbinati 2019). A detailed justification for distinguishing these models, along with their theoretical foundations, can be found primarily - though not exclusively - in the Introductory chapter to the recent analyses of the ESS' democratic module (Ferrin, Kriesi 2025).

One of the key findings from the analyses of the ESS *Democracy Modules* is that *Europeans embrace the other visions or models of democracy (populist, direct and social models of democracy) to a large extent, not as a substitute of the liberal democratic model, but in addition to this model*. The **liberal model of democracy** is understood here as a procedural one that integrates two key components: an electoral dimension – characterized by free and fair elections held at regular intervals – and a liberal dimension, which encompasses civil liberties, a functioning public sphere (essential for democratic elections), the rule of law, and safeguards for minority rights. The **populist model of democracy** prioritizes the will of the people over the views of the elite, disrespects the rights of minorities, and challenges the checks and balances inherent to the liberal model. The **direct model of democracy** posits that citizens should have the final say on important issues by voting directly on them on referenda. Finally, in the **social model of democracy**, governments are supposed to protect citizens against poverty and take measures to reduce differences in income levels (Quaranta 2018).

Hence, while Europeans broadly share an understanding of the procedural electoral dimension of democracy, many of their views also include substantive elements, *above all the idea that the government should protect its citizens against poverty and aim at mitigating social inequalities*. Democracy is considered by many Europeans not just as a set of established procedures but as a means for establishing social justice and/or fulfilling the will of 'the people'.

ESS results on evaluations of democratic performance suggest that citizens' conceptions of democracy are strongly shaped by their lived experience in their own countries. When respondents perceive democratic performance as poor, they become not only more dissatisfied with democracy but also more attentive to its core principles—poor

performance heightens the perceived importance of democratic features. By contrast, strong performance encourages citizens to take these features for granted and to place less emphasis on their importance (Torcal & Tretschel 2016; Kriesi 2025).

Democracies and their variants differ globally (Beetham 1994; Collier & Levitsky 1997). Attitudes toward different models of democracy vary significantly cross-regionally in Europe. Citizens of Western and Northern Europe expect chiefly the elements of the liberal model. As we move towards Eastern and Southern Europe, other models (social/redistributive, direct & populist) grow in importance. Eastern and Southern Europeans expect more from democracy, which makes them more demanding citizens. This seems to be the main source of lower satisfaction with democracy in these countries. Moreover, the highest discrepancy between normative expectations vis-à-vis performance evaluations is to be found in the social/redistributive model of democracy, in Southern and Eastern Europe in particular. Worryingly from the point of view of democratic legitimacy, this discrepancy has grown over the last decade. What is somewhat comforting on the other hand, is that the liberal model is more attractive to an average European today than it was ten years ago (Kriesi 2025).

A decade ago, an effort has been made to compare Western and Central and Eastern Europeans with respect to the gap between citizens' **normative expectations of democracy** and their **evaluations of democratic performance** on those same dimensions (Markowski 2015). The findings yielded four main conclusions. First, conceptions of what democracy ought to be largely confirmed the standard theoretical assumptions: the two most salient components concerned the liberal and electoral dimensions of democracy, namely the expectation that *courts should treat everyone equally* and that *elections should be free and fair*. In this respect, the two parts of Europe differed only marginally. The contrast between the consolidated democracies of Western Europe and the post-communist polities of Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) was limited, and mainly reflected somewhat stronger liberal-democratic expectations in the West.

Second, substantial differences emerged in the evaluation of democratic performance, both overall and across specific dimensions. Assessments were consistently more positive in Western Europe's embedded democracies than in CEE. Consequently, democratic legitimacy—understood here as the degree of congruence between normative expectations and perceived performance—was significantly lower in CEE polities.

Third, a development that appeared especially noteworthy was the growing salience of the **social justice dimension** of democracy, particularly expectations concerning **income equality** and **protection against poverty**. These demands seem likely to remain a durable component of contemporary democratic understandings. Importantly, these two elements are among the most strongly endorsed at the normative level, yet they are also among the most negatively evaluated in terms of actual performance within respondents' own countries.

Fourth, a more fine-grained analysis showed that the largest gaps—out of the 17 democratic attributes examined—between normative expectations and performance evaluations in both Western and Central and Eastern Europe concerned the following items: (1) governments reduce income differences [2.53]¹, (2) governments protect citizens against poverty [2.23], (3) courts treat everyone equally [2.16], (4) governments explain their decisions to voters [1.77], and (5) parties are punished when they perform poorly [1.67]. The broader implication is clear: **the redistributive and social-protective dimensions of democracy constitute a major source of perceived democratic deficit in parts of Europe and are likely to depress democratic legitimacy and satisfaction with democracy in those contexts.**

Subsequent research on the structure of Europeans' conceptions of democracy confirms the foundational status of the liberal model. It also shows that alternative understandings—such as social, direct, and populist models of democracy—are organized hierarchically above this liberal core. This is particularly important for the interpretation of the social-democratic model, since it suggests that social democracy is best understood not as a substitute for liberal democracy, but as a more demanding normative layer built upon it. This interpretation is consistent with the conclusions of the earlier 2016 volume, but is now revalidated a decade later. The central takeaway, therefore, is that **social-democratic expectations remain resilient, yet they are normatively embedded within a broader hierarchy in which liberal democracy continues to serve as the baseline model** (Kriesi 2025: 104–125).

More specifically, the **social-democratic** model of democracy appears to belong to the cluster of “alternative” democratic visions that receive comparatively weaker endorsement among **higher-status** social groups and, by implication, are more salient

¹ The 2.53 numeric expression indicates the gap between Western and Eastern Europeans' differences in the level of normative expectations vis a vis performance fulfilment.

among **lower-status and non-dominant strata** (Cela & Magalhães 2025: 127–154). This finding is important because it situates social-democratic understandings of democracy within the broader terrain of social stratification, suggesting that support for this model is structured not only by ideology but also by position within the social hierarchy.

A further major contribution of the 2025 volume is the argument that evaluations of both liberal and social democracy have become increasingly contingent on **trust in political institutions** and on the experience of **electoral defeat**; these dynamics are, moreover, linked to the spread of **populist values** and rising **affective polarization** (Torcal & Trechsel 2025: 179–205). This is arguably the most important new substantive insight concerning the social-democratic model in the 2025 collection. Evaluations of social democracy are no longer reducible to judgments about welfare provision or distributive equality in a narrow sense. Rather, they increasingly reflect broader assessments of whether citizens regard the political system as **trustworthy**, **responsive**, and **inclusive**, and whether they feel **politically represented** within it.

Palacios (2025: 206–229) adds an important institutional dimension to the relationship between normative democratic expectations and performance evaluations. Her analysis suggests that dissatisfied democrats operating in **low-quality institutional environments** tend to develop more demanding conceptions of democracy. The general proposition is clear: where institutions function effectively, normative democratic commitments are less likely to translate into sharply negative performance evaluations; where institutions are weak or underperforming, dissatisfied citizens raise their expectations and adopt more demanding standards of democratic assessment.

Wessels (2025: 230–250) identifies a further mechanism that is central to the study of democratic legitimacy. If legitimacy is understood as the degree of congruence between what citizens expect from democracy and what they believe democracy actually delivers, then any persistent pattern of **high expectations combined with low perceived performance** constitutes a legitimacy deficit—including in the **social-democratic domain**. In this sense, unmet expectations regarding equality, social protection, and distributive fairness are not peripheral concerns, but integral to the legitimacy of contemporary democratic regimes.

Finally, the politically consequential relationship between democratic models and electoral behavior shows that voters supporting opposition parties are more likely to endorse

the liberal model of democracy, whereas right-wing voters are more likely to reject it (Ferrin, Hernández & Riera 2025: 295–317).

The volume suggests that citizens' evaluations of democratic models—especially their social-democratic dimension—are increasingly mediated by **partisan contestation** and **institutional conflict**, rather than being shaped solely by abstract judgments about distributive outcomes. Although the gap between normative expectations and perceived performance remains substantial, the book does not portray it as having dramatically widened. Rather, its cumulative message is that Europeans remain committed to a conception of democracy that includes a robust social-democratic component, but their assessments of how well democracy delivers on that dimension are increasingly filtered through **political trust**, **affective polarization**, and **institutional quality**.

A decade after the first Democracy Module study, Europeans still do not reduce democracy to a thin liberal-procedural minimum. As the volume's abstract emphasizes, the liberal-democratic model continues to enjoy strong support, but Europeans also endorse “additional models of democracy—for social, direct, and populist democracy” (Ferrin & Kriesi 2025). In other words, the social-democratic model remains a constitutive element of citizens' normative conceptions of democracy rather than a merely secondary ideological supplement.

Moreover, the central message of the 2025 volume largely reproduces the main conclusions of the 2016 study. Europeans do not confine democracy to a narrowly procedural liberal framework; they also attach considerable democratic value to social justice, redistribution, and other social-democratic components. Yet when citizens evaluate how democracy actually functions in their own countries, the social-democratic dimension emerges as the weakest-performing one. As the editors concluded in the earlier volume, “The real democratic deficit in Europe concerns the social democratic vision of democracy. For a majority of citizens in most European countries, their country's democracy does not live up to their expectations in terms of social justice (...) In sum, European democracies need more social democracy if they want to satisfy the view of their citizens as to what democracy should contain” (Kriesi & Morlino 2016: 319).

The decade long ESS two-wave project on models of democracy and their detailed dimensions offers a very general picture of what contemporary Europeans think and feel about the political systems they live in. The two volumes offer numerous insightful results, causal relationships, and contextual impact on the micro-micro dependencies. Yet, a lot

remains to be analyzed further. In particular, our main interest in this article, the generational differences and the impact of age on perceptions of democracy, be it the normative expectations or assessment of their performance is missing. The only exception is a very innovative – both theoretically and empirically - chapter entitled “*Types of liberal democracy and generational shifts: how citizens’ views of democracy differ across generational cohorts*” by Mark Franklin and Pedro Riera (2016). It deserves a longer quote as it can serve as an important starting point for any analyses aimed at analyzing and disentangling the complex generational impacts and the direct influence of age.

“New cohorts of European voters, variously defined, have different attitudes towards the practice of liberal democracy than older cohorts do. (...) But something about those socialized in the framework of the new politics is different from those socialized at an earlier period. And that thing certainly has to do with the way in which elections are conducted, since the socializing treatment differs across country cohorts uniquely in terms of the nature of electoral contestation that different cohorts experience when they are being politically socialized. Our findings build on the idea that there are distinctions between voters in how they evaluate political institutions but suggest a new way of defining these distinctions, in terms of the way in which representation is seen to occur by different cohorts of voters in different types of system. The relevant distinctions are not simple ones, impacting all citizens of a given country equally, and they do not relate purely to the current situation experienced by the voters of a country. (...) Apparently the logic of representation in the system concerned is easily grasped – at least by voters who have not become used to a different logic – since young voters seemingly are able to understand new realities as these come into being. Much prior work has emphasized the importance of socialization processes on political values and behavior (...) What we add to prior findings is a theoretical basis for expecting interactions between early socialization and contemporary context, focusing on distinctions between voters socialized in different electoral periods – before or after the sea change that accompanied the decline of cleavage politics in many countries – and confirming those expectations with new findings. Such cohort differences evidently still characterize the world we live in today, bringing into the present values inculcated by circumstances long past. Despite repeated insistence on the importance of cohort differences by Inglehart, Putnam and others, these differences are routinely ignored, leading in many cases to inconclusive or contradictory findings. Our comparative findings in this chapter clearly supersedes this previous literature by reminding us yet again of the importance of socializing influences and the resulting cohort differences that can muddy findings in areas far removed from those in which such differences have previously been theorized in principle or found in practice (Franklin & Riera 2016: 127-9).

In a nutshell, younger cohorts of European citizens have different attitudes to electoral representation than older cohorts, because they have been socialized into a different type of (electoral) democracy.

In the 2025 volume digesting the 2021/22 data the impact of age is very scarce. The only testing applies to its general impact on the four models of democracy, as Kriesi (2025: 184-5) submits that **age is non-linearly related to several conceptions of democracy**. More specifically, the results indicate an inverted curvilinear U-shaped relationship between age and the importance attributed to liberal, direct, and populist models of democracy. This pattern suggests that **respondents at both ends of the age distribution—the youngest and the oldest—are less likely than those in the middle age ranges to assign very high importance to liberal democracy. In contrast, for the social-democratic model, the curvilinear effect of age is not statistically significant in ESS Round 10.**

Taken together, the existing literature suggests that democratic satisfaction is shaped not only by institutional performance but also by the relationship between citizens' expectations and their perceptions of how democracy works in practice.

3. Research Questions and Hypotheses

This article builds on an expectation–performance framework of democratic legitimacy. Citizens evaluate democracy not only according to how institutions perform but also according to whether this performance meets their normative expectations regarding what democracy should deliver. Satisfaction with democracy therefore depends on the congruence between expectations and perceived performance: when democratic institutions meet citizens’ expectations satisfaction increases, while unmet expectations generate dissatisfaction. The hypotheses below test this expectation–performance mechanism while examining how it varies across generations, European regions, and over time, thereby shedding new light on generational differences in the sources of democratic satisfaction in contemporary Europe.

The specific research questions (RQ) addressed in this article are as follows:

RQ1: How are *normative expectations / performance evaluations / democratic deficits*² (differences between expectations and evaluations) on specific dimensions of democracy associated with satisfaction with democracy?

RQ2: Do the relationships specified in RQ1 vary by: *age groups / European regions / in time (2012-2022)*?

These two key RQs can be cautiously disentangled into more detailed hypotheses.

² Part of the scholars who created and interpreted the two ESS Democracy Modules propose that the discrepancy between particular democratic elements’ normative expectations vis a vis their performance evaluations are indicators of political legitimacy (see Wessels 2016; 2025; Markowski 2016)

Hypotheses:

At first, normative expectations towards democracy – without taking into account evaluations of democratic performance – can be understood as a sign of democratic commitment and thus we might expect a positive correlation with satisfaction with democracy. Hence, we hypothesize that:

H1.1 The higher the general expectation towards democracy as an ideal political regime one considers it worth living in, the higher the satisfaction with democracy.

The following hypothesis takes into account not just the general expectation of democracy as an ideal (as H1.1) but looks at average support for more detailed expectations regarding particular dimensions of democracy – such as rule of law, free and fair elections, protection of minority rights or accountability of the government. We expect – again, without taking into account performance evaluations just yet – that:

H1.2 The higher the average level of the detailed normative expectations towards key elements of democracy, the higher the overall satisfaction with democracy.

Now, following the arguments put forward in the theoretical background, we have good reasons to suspect that:

H1.3 The higher the level of the normative expectations towards the liberal (rather than direct or social) components of democracy, the higher the overall satisfaction with democracy.

Moving on to democratic performance evaluations, a fairly straightforward hypothesis is that:

H2. The higher the performance evaluations of specific dimensions of democracy, the higher the overall satisfaction with democracy.

Now, citizens judge democracy not only by performance but by how well performance matches their normative expectations of what democracy should deliver. In this sense,

fulfilled expectations should result in higher satisfaction with democracy, and unfulfilled expectations should translate into lower satisfaction. This expectation-performance gap hypothesis takes the following form:

H3. The larger the gap between citizens' normative expectations and their evaluations of democratic performance, the lower their satisfaction with democracy.

Finally, while hypothesis H3 accounts for expectation–performance gap it does not include the interaction between expectations and performance. The expectation-performance gap (democratic deficit) framework of H3 captures the absolute mismatch – without discriminating whether expectations are high or low –, while interaction captures conditional expectations that do take that into account. The basic logic behind the hypothesis H4 is the following: the more one thinks something is important for democracy, the higher the satisfaction with democracy, but only if this is a fulfilled normative expectation – it is accompanied by high evaluation of democratic performance on this dimension. If – on the contrary – the expectation is unfulfilled, the more important a certain dimension is, the lower the level of satisfaction with democracy will be.

H4. The effect of normative expectations on satisfaction with democracy depends on perceived democratic performance: higher expectations increase satisfaction when performance evaluations are high but decrease satisfaction when performance evaluations are low.

We also aim at assessing whether the expectation-performance gaps and its conditional effects affect satisfaction with democracy dependent on age (young vs. old), time (2012 vs. 2022), and region (Western, Northern, Southern, Central/Eastern Europe). Assessing the precise mechanisms driving all of these differences is impossible in a single paper. In this sense, this is more an empirical endeavor than an assessment of some causal mechanism. However, given the importance of the social-democratic model of democracy underscored in the theoretical section, we do propose a final set of hypotheses related to the temporal evolution of social-democratic expectations by age and region.

During the aftermath of the Great Recession,³ democratic legitimacy in Europe became strongly linked to governments' capacity to provide economic protection and social redistribution. Consequently, gaps between citizens' social-democratic expectations and perceived performance should have been particularly consequential for democratic satisfaction during this period, especially in the crisis-hit economies of Southern Europe (Cordero & Simón, 2016) and among economically exposed cohorts, particularly the young and the middle-aged (Rama & Cordero, 2018). Our final set of hypotheses reads as follows:

H5. Unmet social-democratic expectations will have a stronger negative effect on satisfaction with democracy in 2012 than in 2022.

H5.1. This effect will be stronger in Southern Europe.

H5.2. This effect will be stronger among younger and middle-aged citizens.

4. Data and Methods

In our analyses, we rely on survey data from two waves of a large-scale comparative public opinion survey: the European Social Survey (ESS). ESS is an academically driven cross-national survey, founded in 2001, and administered in 40 countries to date. It involves strict random probability sampling, high response rate and rigorous translation protocols. One might say that it is the gold standard for public opinion surveys in Europe. We use data from two waves – with data collected between 2010 and 2012 (6th wave) and between 2020 and 2022 (10th wave) – in which a specific module of attitudes towards democracy is included. To the best of our knowledge, this is the only dataset that allows for comparison of the effects

³ While the Great Recession occurred between late 2007 and 2009 in most countries, its economic consequences (the so-called 'Eurozone debt crisis' of 2010-2012) lasted longer – even a decade in terms of unemployment levels in Southern Europe – and thus the 2012 ESS wave measures considerably well the aftermath of that financial crisis. It should be also acknowledged that, in the 2022 ESS wave, the Covid pandemic could be a confounding variable. Unfortunately, the data from ESS Democracy module is available only at these two points in time.

of normative expectations and performance evaluations across time covering most European countries and thus allowing for sufficient sample sizes to assess these effects by age groups and regions. For the sake of parsimony, from now on we will refer to ESS 06 data as “2012” and ESS 10 data as “2022”.

To make the comparison between two waves meaningful, we focus on countries for which we have data in both timeframes. The following countries are included in the analyses: Belgium, France, Germany, Great Britain, Ireland, the Netherlands, Switzerland (Western Europe); Finland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden (Northern Europe); Cyprus, Italy, Portugal, Spain (Southern Europe); and Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Lithuania, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia (Central and Eastern Europe).

We distinguish these four regions – Western Europe (WE), Northern Europe (NE) and Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) – following the reasoning exposed elsewhere (Markowski & Zagórski 2025).⁴ The differences between regions in satisfaction with democracy, support for democracy and normative expectations towards democracy are significant.⁵

Age is operationalized using four groups: 18–24, 25–34, 35–64, and 65+. This categorization reflects both theoretical and empirical considerations. Political socialization research suggests that political attitudes crystallize during the “impressionable years” of late adolescence and early adulthood, roughly from the late teens to the mid-twenties or early thirties (Jennings & Niemi 1981; Alwin & Krosnick 1991). Distinguishing the 18–24 group therefore captures citizens who are still within or immediately after this formative period, while the 25–34 category represents early adulthood when attitudes begin to stabilize. We want to focus on the young particularly given the scope of the YouthDecide 2040 project with the key argument here being that first-time voters and individuals in the formative socialization stage behave differently from slightly older young adults. The remaining categories correspond to later life-cycle stages, with individuals aged 35–64 typically representing mid-life adults with stable social and economic positions, and those aged 65+ representing older cohorts whose political behaviour and regime evaluations often differ systematically due to life-course and generational factors. Similar age groupings are commonly used in comparative survey research, facilitating comparability with existing

⁴ We do not include “New Europe” here due to lack of comparable data across the two timeframes.

⁵ For a detailed analysis of between and within variance in democratic attitudes across these regions see Appendix A, in which the only non-significant cross-regional differences we find are for the normative expectation about “free and fair elections” for the young.

studies. These categories reflect meaningful life-course stages and ensure sufficient sample sizes.

The only dependent variable is general satisfaction with democracy, measured with the standard question “On the whole, how satisfied are you with the way democracy works in [country]?” on an 11-point scale where 0 is “Extremely dissatisfied” and 10 “Extremely satisfied”.

Our key independent variables are the following: support for democracy as a regime type, (detailed) normative expectations towards democracy, (detailed) democratic performance evaluations and the expectations-performance gap we call ‘democratic deficit’. Support for democracy as an ideal regime type is operationalized using the following question on importance of living in a democracy: “How important is it for you to live in a country that is governed democratically?” on an 11-point scale where 0 is “Not important at all” and 10 “Extremely important”. The operationalization of normative expectations towards different dimensions of democracy is gathered in Table 1. We include only those dimensions that were included in both waves of the survey (hence, we exclude the populist dimensions measured only in wave 10). In most analyses we evaluate these dimensions separately – due to the fact that they are highly correlated. For testing hypothesis H1.2, we take the average value for all 9 items.

Table 1. Normative expectations towards different dimensions of democracy

Wording	Concept measured	Model of democracy
How important do you think it is for democracy in general...		
...that national elections are free and fair?	Free and fair elections	Liberal democracy
...that different political parties offer clear alternatives to one another?	Party alternatives	Liberal democracy
...that the media are free to criticise the government?	Free media	Liberal democracy
...that the rights of minority groups are protected?	Minority rights	Liberal democracy
...that citizens have the final say on the most important political issues by voting on them directly in referendums?	Referendums	Direct democracy
...that the courts treat everyone the same?	Rule of law	Liberal democracy
...that governing parties are punished in elections when they have done a bad job?	Accountability	Liberal democracy
...that the government protects all citizens against poverty?	Protection of the poor	Social democracy
...that the government takes measures to reduce differences in income levels?	Redistribution	Social democracy

Source: ESS 6 and ESS 10. Note: 11-point scale for all items: 0=Not at all important for democracy in general; 10=Extremely important for democracy in general

Evaluations of performance on different dimensions of democracy follow the same structure as normative expectations with respondents being asked to what extent they think these apply to the way democracy is working in their country at the time of the survey. For example, for the first item, the wording is “National elections in [country] are free and fair” with responses on an 11-point scale, where 0 means “Does not apply at all” and 10 “Applies completely”.

Democratic deficit (expectation-performance gap) on these same dimensions of democracy is measured by a simple subtraction of numerical values of performance from values of expectations at the individual level, resulting in a variable ranging from -10 (lowest expectation and highest performance) to 10 (highest expectation and lowest performance).

Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) linear regressions are employed to assess our hypotheses. ESS-recommended analysis weights are applied. We control only for country fixed effects – to make sure that the results are not driven by a certain country – and for gender – to, on top of including a standard sociodemographic control – account for the fact that young males and females have increasingly divergent paths regarding democracy, and especially far-right voting (Miloslav et al. 2026; Dolci 2026). It is important to note that we do not focus on any gendered effects here. We model the direct effects of our IVs, the effects of our IVs with the four age groups (with the modal category of 35-64 as reference), and, finally to account for the effects of normative expectations conditional on performance evaluations, we include models in which an interaction of expectations*evaluations is included.

5. Results

5.1. Descriptive analysis: satisfaction with democracy, support for democracy, normative expectations towards democracy, democratic performance evaluations, and democratic deficits (expectation-performance gaps)

First, we present some descriptive data about our key variables. Starting with the dependent variable, overall, levels of **satisfaction with democracy** (SWD from now on) are higher in 2022 compared to 2012. Disaggregating the general results by age and region sheds more light on the evolution of SWD in this timeframe. It seems that, at both points in time, there is a curvilinear relationship between SWD and age – with the youngest and the oldest European citizens being visibly more satisfied with democracy than the middle aged (see Figure 1). The young – especially the youngest (18-24) – tend to be more satisfied with democracy than the middle-aged, especially in WE and CE, but not in SE, where the oldest come out as most satisfied. On the other hand, those aged 25-34 are the least satisfied group of all in SE in both 2012 and 2022, and in NE, the 25-34 group is the one that has become most disillusioned by democracy in this period. In CEE, both groups of the young have seen their satisfaction levels drop significantly. On the contrary, in SE, a strong increase in satisfaction is observed among all age groups. Overall, we see most significant changes in CEE (among the young) and SE (among all age groups).

Figure 1. Marginal effects of age groups on satisfaction with democracy, 2012 (left) and 2022 (right)

Source: own elaboration based on ESS06 and ESS10. *Note:* Marginal effect of age groups calculated from separate OLS regressions for each region, controlling for gender and country fixed effects.

Considering general **support for democracy**, the young – on average – think it is less important to live in a democracy than the old across all regions of Europe (see figure 2a). Support for democracy has increased across all regions and age groups, but more so among the old (see figure 2b). The strongest growth is to be found among the old in CEE and SE. Interestingly, in NE, support for democracy has increased to a greater degree among the youngest group.

Figure 2a. Support for democracy by age group and region, ESS10 2022 mean values

Source: own elaboration based on ESS06 and ESS10.

Figure 3b. Support for democracy by age group and region, 2012-2022 difference in mean values

Source: own elaboration based on ESS06 and ESS10.

As far as **normative expectations towards democracy** are concerned, broadly speaking, the young expect from democracy less than their older counterparts (see figures 3a, 3b, and 3c). Moreover, the different dimensions of democracy taken together, the young expect from democracy less in 2022 compared to 2012. The only dimension on which the young expect more from democracy than their older counterparts in 2022 is minority rights (but, significantly, not in CEE).

Support for social-democratic and direct models of democracy has fallen considerably between 2012 and 2022. Social-democratic redistributive model of democracy stands out as less prevalent among the young, particularly in NE and CEE (for instance, in Poland, there is a drop of nearly 3 points on an 11-points scale among the youngest group). Support for redistribution as a normative dimension of democracy has decreased substantially in all regions but WE.

Accountability seems to matter less to the young, as there is a strong and positive linear effect of age on the importance of accountability both in 2012 and 2022. It also matters less in 2022 compared to 2012 for the young but not as much for the oldest. Accountability is, overall, less important in Northern Europe (NE) and more relevant in Southern Europe (SE) and CEE. It has become less relevant in all regions but CEE between 2012-2022.

Support for the key dimensions of free and fair elections and rule of law is the highest across regions and remains stable over time. Support for free media has also seen an increase in support especially for the youngest and oldest groups, in all regions but CEE. Taken together, the strongest decline in normative expectations across several dimensions is to be found in SE and CEE.

Figure 4a. Normative expectations of democracy by age group, ESS10 2022 mean values

Figure 5b. Differences between ESS06 (2012) and ESS10 (2022) in normative expectations of democracy by age group, difference in mean values.

Figure 6c. Differences between ESS06 (2012) and ESS10 (2022) in normative expectations about several dimensions of democracy by region, difference in mean values (total).

Source: own elaboration based on ESS06 and ESS10.

Regarding **performance evaluations and democratic deficits** (difference between expectation and evaluation), as Table 2 shows, on average, the young evaluate democratic performance slightly worse than their older counterparts. Nonetheless, given that their expectations are also lower, the expectation-performance gap is not bigger for the young. There is however a substantial difference between the two groups of the young – for those aged 18-24 the deficit is usually the smallest (together with the elderly), while for the 25-34 it is often the highest, but the differences are quite small. Overall, in 2022, dimensions on which democracy seems to struggle the most – in terms of individual expectations-performance gaps – is in the defense of rule of law (total deficit of 4.0), protecting the poor (3.9), redistribution (3.3), and direct democracy (3.3).

Table 2. Normative expectations, performance evaluations and democratic deficits by age groups, mean values, all countries, 2022

Dimension	Variable	Age				Total
		18-24	25-34	35-64	65+	
Free and fair elections	Expectation	8.8	9.0	9.0	9.0	9.0
	Evaluation	7.0	7.0	7.2	7.5	7.2
	<i>Deficit (expectation - evaluation)</i>	1.8	2.0	1.8	1.5	1.7
Alternative party offer	Expectation	7.7	7.9	7.9	7.9	7.9
	Evaluation	5.7	5.4	5.5	5.8	5.6
	<i>Deficit (expectation - evaluation)</i>	2.0	2.5	2.4	2.1	2.3
Media freedom	Expectation	8.2	8.4	8.4	8.2	8.3
	Evaluation	6.6	6.4	6.7	7.1	6.8
	<i>Deficit (expectation - evaluation)</i>	1.6	2.0	1.7	1.1	1.6
Protection of minority rights	Expectation	8.4	8.4	8.3	8.1	8.3
	Evaluation	5.9	5.8	6.1	6.3	6.1
	<i>Deficit (expectation - evaluation)</i>	2.5	2.6	2.2	1.8	2.2
Referendums	Expectation	7.8	7.8	7.9	7.9	7.9
	Evaluation	4.5	4.2	4.5	5.0	4.6
	<i>Deficit (expectation - evaluation)</i>	3.3	3.6	3.4	2.9	3.3
Rule of Law	Expectation	9.0	9.1	9.2	9.1	9.2
	Evaluation	5.2	5.1	5.2	5.2	5.2
	<i>Deficit (expectation - evaluation)</i>	3.9	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0
Accountability	Expectation	7.7	8.0	8.4	8.5	8.3
	Evaluation	4.6	4.4	5.0	5.7	5.1
	<i>Deficit (expectation - evaluation)</i>	3.2	3.7	3.3	2.8	3.2
Protection of the poor	Expectation	8.3	8.4	8.5	8.5	8.5
	Evaluation	4.5	4.3	4.5	4.7	4.5
	<i>Deficit (expectation - evaluation)</i>	3.8	4.1	4.0	3.8	3.9
Redistribution	Expectation	7.4	7.6	7.7	7.9	7.7
	Evaluation	4.6	4.3	4.4	4.6	4.5
	<i>Deficit (expectation - evaluation)</i>	2.9	3.3	3.3	3.2	3.3

Source: own elaboration based on ESS10.

Several cross-regional differences stand out (results not shown here). In general, the deficits are lower in NE and WE. In both SE and CEE, the biggest expectation-evaluation gap is related to concerns about the rule of law (5.0 in SE, 5.4 in CEE), with deficits equally distributed among age groups in CEE, and somewhat less pronounced for the young in SE. The second highest deficit in both regions relates to the government not protecting the poor well enough – especially in the eyes of the young. Additionally, in CEE, the young are also concerned about the lack of accountability and limited direct democracy.

5.2. Analyses of the effects of support for democracy, normative expectations towards democracy, democratic performance evaluations and democratic deficits (expectation-performance gaps) on satisfaction with democracy

What follows are results of analyses directly aimed at testing our hypotheses. In every part of it, we will also include an analysis of heterogeneity of the hypothesized effects by age group.

Starting with the first set of hypotheses, we first present evidence regarding *H1.1 The higher the general expectation towards democracy as an ideal political regime one considers it worth living in, the higher the satisfaction with the performance of democracy.*

Overall, we do find that the higher the **general support for democracy** as an ideal regime the higher the general satisfaction with the performance of democracy. With an increase of 1 on a scale from 0 to 10 in support for democracy (importance of living in a democracy), satisfaction with democratic performance increases 0.28 – on an 11-point scale – in 2012 and 0.26 in 2022 (Figure 4a). This positive relationship holds across all age groups but – notably – it is less pronounced among the young only in 2022 (Fig 4b).

Figure 7a. Marginal effects of support for democracy as an ideal on SWD, 2012 (left) and 2022 (right)

Source: ESS06 & ESS10. Note: Marginal effect of support for democracy from OLS regressions, controlling for gender and country fixed effects.

Figure 8b. Marginal effects of support for democracy as an ideal on SWD by age groups, 2012 (left) and 2022 (right)

Source: ESS06 & ESS10. Note: Marginal effect of interaction term between support for democracy and age groups from OLS regressions controlling for gender and country fixed effects.

H1.2 The higher the average level of the detailed normative expectations towards key elements of democracy, the higher the overall satisfaction with the performance of democracy.

The **average level of normative expectations towards detailed aspects of democracy** has a positive effect on satisfaction with the performance of democracy which is more pronounced in 2022 (0.07) compared to 2012 (0.05) (Fig 5a). The disaggregated effects by age are quite telling in this case (Fig 5b). For those aged 25-34 the effects are null in both 2012 and 2022. For the other groups the effect is positive and, while in 2012, the slopes of the youngest and the oldest are practically equal, in 2022, the stronger relationship between expectations and SWD among the oldest group stands out.

Figure 9a. Marginal effects of normative expectations (average of nine items) on SWD, 2012 (left) and 2022 (right) (from a model controlling for gender and country fixed effects)

Source: ESS06 & ESS10. Note: Marginal effect of average of 9 items of normative expectations from OLS regressions, controlling for gender and country fixed effects.

Figure 10b. Marginal effects of normative expectations (average of nine items) on SWD by age groups, 2012 (left) and 2022 (right)

Source: ESS06 & ESS10. Note: Marginal effect of interaction term between the average of 9 items of normative expectations and age groups from OLS regressions, controlling for gender and country fixed effects.

H3. The larger the gap between citizens' normative expectations and their evaluations of democratic performance, the lower their satisfaction with democracy.

Table 3 gathers the results of a series of regressions aimed at assessing **the effects of normative expectations, performance evaluations and the expectation-evaluation gap (democratic deficit) for each dimension of democracy separately**. We also include, on top of the direct effects, the assessment of heterogeneity of these effects by age groups (with models interacting the dimension with age group). The direct effect of deficits is always negative, both in 2012 and 2022, and across all age groups, with less pronounced negative effects for the young in 2022 on the following dimensions: party alternatives, free media, accountability, protection of the poor, and redistribution.

Several additional findings gathered in Table 3 stand out:

- Rule of law as normative democratic dimension has a stronger positive relationship with satisfaction with democracy in 2022 compared to 2012, especially for the middle-aged and the elderly.
- Association of the importance of accountability for democracy is positive but not significant in 2012 and in 2022 it becomes negative and significant. In 2022, evaluation of accountability seems to affect satisfaction with democracy to a lesser degree for those aged 18-24 and 65+, while in 2012 there were no significant differences across age groups in this regard.
- Association of the importance of government protecting the poor for democracy is negative for all citizens in 2012 but it becomes positive and significant for the oldest group in 2022. In 2022, those aged 65+ are more satisfied with democracy the more they think that the government protects the poor is important for democracy. This was not the case in 2012, when the direct effect of importance of this dimension for democracy was negative independently of age. It is only in 2022 when evaluations of government protecting the poor and redistributing are less associated with satisfaction with democracy for the youngest.
- In 2012, positive evaluation of protection of minority rights is associated positively with satisfaction with democracy to a greater degree among those aged 24-35, while in 2022 it seems slightly less relevant for those aged 18-25 and 65+, compared to the middle-aged.

Table 3. Effects on satisfaction with democracy: summary of findings for 2012 and 2022.

Dimension of democracy	Effects on satisfaction with democracy of:											
	Normative expectation				Performance evaluation				Difference expectation - evaluation (deficit)			
	ESS year	Direct effect	Differences (interactions)	by age	Direct effect	Differences (interactions)	by age	Direct effect	Differences (interactions)	by age		
National elections are free and fair	2012	+	- for 25-34		+	ns.		-	- 25-34			
	2022	+	- for 18-24		+	ns.		-	ns.			
Different political parties offer clear alternatives to one another	2012	+	n.s.		+	ns.		-	ns.			
	2022	+	n.s.		+	- for 18-24 & 65+		-	+ for 18-24 & 65+			
The media are free to criticise the government	2012	+	n.s.		+	ns.		-	ns.			
	2022	+	n.s.		+	- for 18-24		-	+ for 18-24			
The rights of minority groups are protected	2012	+	n.s.		+	+ for 25-34		-	ns.			
	2022	+	n.s.		+	- for 18-34 & 65+		-	+ for 65+			
Citizens have the final say on political issues by voting directly in referendum	2012	-	+ for 65+		+	- for 65+		-	+ for 65+			
	2022	-	+ for 18-24 & 65+		+	- for 65+		-	+ for 65+			
The courts treat everyone the same	2012	n.s.	n.s.		+	- for 65+		-	ns.			
	2022	+	n.s.		+	- for 65+		-	+ for 65+			
Governing parties are punished in elections when they have done a bad job	2012	-	n.s.		+	ns.		-	ns.			
	2022	-	n.s.		+	- for 18-24 & 65+		-	+ for 18-24			
The government protects all citizens against poverty	2012	-	n.s.		+	ns.		-	ns.			
	2022	n.s.	+ for 65+		+	- for 18-24		-	+ for 18-24 & 25-34			
The government takes measures to reduce differences in income levels	2012	-	n.s.		+	ns.		-	ns.			
	2022	n.s.	+ for 25-34 & 65+		+	- for 18-24		-	+ for 18-24 & 25-34			

Source: own elaboration based on ESS06 & ESS10 data. *Notes:* Results gathered from multiple linear regression models of direct and interactive effects. Differences by age always refer to the middle-aged group (35-64 years old).

Moving on to the **conditional effects**, Figure 6 gathers the marginal effects of the **interaction between expectations and evaluations** on SWD, across all age groups for 2022.

Figure 11. Marginal effects on SWD of normative expectations towards different dimensions of democracy by evaluation of performance on these dimensions (expectations x evaluations interaction term). All age groups. 2022.

Source: own elaboration based on ESS10. Note: Marginal effect of interaction term between expectations and evaluations from OLS regressions, controlling for gender and country fixed effects.

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Broadly speaking, if expectations are aligned with evaluations – the more one expects and the better one evaluates – the higher the satisfaction. However, while fulfilled expectations might drive higher satisfaction, unfulfilled expectations might also depress it. It can also happen at the same time, rendering the overall direct effect non-significant. This is, for instance, the case of normative expectation of “Free and fair elections dimension” – which, in 2022, drives both higher satisfaction among those who evaluate it positively (the slope is over the zero-effect line to the right of the axis) as well as lower satisfaction among those who evaluate country’s performance on this negatively (the slope is below the zero-effect line to the left of the axis). **Therefore, on the one hand, we can say that normative expectations about the following dimensions boost satisfaction with democracy if they are fulfilled: “alternative in political offer”, “protection of minority rights”, “government protects the poor”, and “government reduces inequalities”. On the other hand, the following expectations depress satisfaction when unfulfilled: “freedom of media”, “referendums”, and “accountability”.**

Do the conditional effects vary by age? To some degree, at least in 2022. As Figure 7 shows, fulfilled normative expectation of free and fair elections boost satisfaction with democracy only among the middle-aged and the elderly. The youngest group stands out as the one for which satisfaction with democracy increases to a greater degree with fulfilled expectations regarding media freedom, referendums, rule of law, accountability and redistribution (the latter together with the 25-34 group).

In Figure 8, only the effects for the 18-24 group are plotted for the sake of visibility. Significant positive effects on satisfaction with democracy are to be found among the youngest if their normative expectation about minority rights, redistribution and – to a lower degree – rule of law and alternatives in political offer. Contrarily, unfulfilled expectations about direct democracy, accountability, and media freedom hinder democratic satisfaction of the youngest, but the same applies to all other age groups.

Figure 9 plots these same interactive effects but this time for the group aged 24-35. Similarly to the youngest groups satisfaction with democracy receives a boost from fulfilled expectations about minority rights protection and redistribution. What is striking about the 25-34 years-old group is that fulfillment of normative expectation about political alternatives is not relevant at all for their satisfaction with democracy.

Figure 12. Marginal effects on SWD of normative expectations about different dimensions of democracy by evaluation of performance on these dimensions (interaction term). Separate models by age groups. 2022.

Source: own elaboration based on ESS10. Note: Marginal effect of interaction term between expectations and evaluations by age groups from OLS regressions, controlling for gender and country fixed effects.

Figure 13. Marginal effects on satisfaction with democracy of normative expectations about different dimensions of democracy by evaluation of performance on these dimensions (interaction term). The youngest (18-24 years old). 2022.

Source: own elaboration based on ESS10. Note: Marginal effect of interaction term between expectations and evaluations from OLS regressions, controlling for gender and country fixed effects.

Figure 14. Marginal effects on satisfaction with democracy of normative expectations about different dimensions of democracy by evaluation of performance on these dimensions (interaction term). The relatively young (25-34 years old), 2022.

Source: own elaboration based on ESS10. Note: Marginal effect of interaction term between expectations and evaluations from OLS regressions, controlling for gender and country fixed effects.

In short, in 2022: (1) free and fair elections matter more for the satisfaction with democracy among older groups; (2) unfulfilled expectations about referendums and accountability hinder satisfaction with democracy across all age groups; and (3) minority rights and redistribution expectations – if fulfilled – boost satisfaction with democracy, especially among the young.

Do these effects vary in time? The key differences we find between 2012 (see Figure 10) and 2022 are the following: (1) elections matter less for democratic satisfaction among the youngest in 2022 compared to 2012; (2) minority rights mattered in 2012 and still matter today, even more so for the boost in satisfaction with democracy among the youngest; (3) supporters of direct democracy with unfulfilled expectations were dissatisfied with democracy in 2012 and still are in 2022; (4) accountability did not matter as much in 2012 but it hinders democratic satisfaction in 2022 independently of age; (5) social-democratic normative expectations of protecting the poor and redistribution were not significant in 2012, but in 2022 they are, especially so for the young who see their wills fulfilled.

Do they hold across regions? Figures 11 and 12 plot the interactive effect of expectations and performance by age for Southern Europe and for Central and Eastern Europe separately (for 2022). In 2022, the more the young in SE expect from democracy and the more they think it delivers in protecting minority rights, the more satisfied with democracy they are. Same does not apply to older generations in that region. For CEE, the biggest differences across age categories in conditional effects on SWD of normative expectations concerns free and fair elections and the rule of law. Those aged 25-34 seem to be less satisfied with democracy if their the higher their expectations and evaluation of performance of democracies in that region regarding free and fair elections. As far as rule of law is concerned, high expectations married with high performance evaluations boost democratic satisfaction among both groups of the young, contrarily to the older groups.

Figure 15. Marginal effects on SWD of normative expectations about different dimensions of democracy by evaluation of performance on these dimensions (interaction term). Separate models by age groups. 2012.

Source: own elaboration based on ESS06. Note: Marginal effect of interaction term between expectations and evaluations by age groups from OLS regressions, controlling for gender and country fixed effects.

Figure 16. Marginal effects on SWD of normative expectations about different dimensions of democracy by evaluation of performance on these dimensions (interaction term). Separate models by age groups. 2022. Southern Europe.

Source: own elaboration based on ESS10. Note: Marginal effect of interaction term between expectations and evaluations by age groups from OLS regressions, controlling for gender and country fixed effects.

Figure 17. Marginal effects on SWD of normative expectations about different dimensions of democracy by evaluation of performance on these dimensions (interaction term). Separate models by age groups. 2022. Central and Eastern Europe.

Source: own elaboration based on ESS10. Note: Marginal effect of interaction term between expectations and evaluations by age groups from OLS regressions, controlling for gender and country fixed effects.

Taken together, the empirical analyses provide substantial support for the core expectations of the expectation–performance framework. First, both general democratic commitment and detailed normative expectations are positively associated with satisfaction with democracy (SWD), confirming H1.1 and H1.2. Citizens who attach greater importance to democracy as a regime and to its institutional components tend to report higher levels of satisfaction with how democracy works in their country. This relationship is, however, uneven across age groups, with the association largely absent among the 25–34 cohort and becoming particularly pronounced among older citizens in 2022. Second, consistent with H2, positive evaluations of democratic performance across institutional dimensions are strongly and consistently associated with higher satisfaction with democracy. Third, and most importantly, the expectation–performance gap behaves as predicted: larger democratic deficits are systematically associated with lower satisfaction with democracy across nearly all dimensions and time points, providing clear support for H3. Finally, the interaction analyses corroborate the conditional logic proposed in H4. Normative expectations increase satisfaction with democracy when citizens perceive democratic performance as high, but depress satisfaction when perceived performance is low. This pattern is particularly visible for dimensions such as media freedom, referendums, and accountability, where unmet expectations significantly reduce democratic satisfaction.

The analyses also reveal meaningful variation across age groups and over time. In 2022, fulfilled expectations regarding minority rights and redistribution are particularly consequential for democratic satisfaction among younger citizens, whereas institutional dimensions such as free and fair elections matter more for older cohorts.

Finally, the results provide partial support for the temporal and contextual expectations formulated in H5. The negative impact of unmet social-democratic expectations - particularly those related to redistribution and protection of the poor - appears stronger in 2012 than in 2022, consistent with the idea that economic performance played a particularly central role in shaping democratic legitimacy in the aftermath of the Great Recession. This pattern is especially visible in Southern Europe and among younger and middle-aged citizens, lending support to H5a and H5b.

Overall, these findings indicate that satisfaction with democracy depends not only on how citizens evaluate democratic performance but also on how closely these evaluations match their normative expectations regarding what democracy should be.

6. Conclusions

This study set out to examine how normative expectations, performance evaluations, and expectation–performance gaps shape satisfaction with democracy across European regions and generations. The findings provide strong empirical support for the expectation–performance framework of democratic legitimacy. Satisfaction with democracy depends not only on how citizens evaluate democratic performance of their countries but also on whether democracy fulfills the normative expectations regarding what democratic governance should deliver.

Across virtually all democratic dimensions examined, larger expectation–performance gaps are associated with lower satisfaction with democracy. **Citizens who believe that democracy fails to deliver key democratic attributes – such as fair elections, rule of law, or social protection – are significantly more likely to express dissatisfaction with how democracy works in their country.** This confirms that perceived democratic deficits play a central role in shaping democratic legitimacy.

At the same time, the results reveal meaningful generational variation in how citizens evaluate democracy. Younger Europeans tend to attach greater importance to minority rights and redistributive outcomes when assessing democratic performance, whereas older citizens' satisfaction depends more strongly on institutional guarantees such as elections and rule of law. **These findings suggest that different generations prioritize different components of democratic governance when evaluating the quality of democracy.**

The analysis also highlights important temporal dynamics. In the aftermath of the Great Recession, unmet expectations regarding redistribution and social protection were particularly consequential for democratic satisfaction, especially in Southern Europe and among younger and middle-aged citizens. By 2022, however, the influence of these social-economic expectations appears to have weakened somewhat relative to other democratic dimensions.

Taken together, the results indicate that democratic legitimacy in contemporary European countries cannot be understood solely in terms of performance of particular

elements of democracy. **Instead, legitimacy depends on the relationship between performance of democracy in particular domains and citizens' evolving normative expectations towards these domains.** As different generations prioritize different democratic principles, the sources of democratic satisfaction – and dissatisfaction – are likely to change over time.

Additionally, youth differ across Europe. The youngest group (18–24) shows visibly different preferences compared with young adults (25–34), and both groups vary by the region or country in which they live. From other studies, we also know that young women differ from young men. In short, one should avoid speaking of “European youth” as a single, monolithic entity, because it does not exist. Nevertheless, there are a number of traits that clearly distinguish younger people from older generations.

An important question raised by these findings is whether the stronger association between minority rights and redistributive outcomes and satisfaction with democracy among younger citizens reflects specifically left-leaning preferences, or broader cross-ideological salience. While the present analysis does not explicitly model ideology, the evidence suggests that these patterns should not be interpreted narrowly as partisan effects. The expectation–performance framework captures the importance attributed to democratic attributes rather than specific policy positions, and prior research (e.g. Svallfors 2012; Ferrin, Hernández & Riera 2025) shows that inclusion-related dimensions of democracy tend to enjoy broad normative support across ideological divides. The findings are therefore more consistent with a generational reweighting of democratic priorities than with a simple ideological shift.

At first glance, these results may appear to contrast with claims that younger cohorts are more open to authoritarian alternatives. However, these patterns are not necessarily contradictory. Younger citizens may express weaker attachment to procedural aspects of liberal democracy while maintaining strong support for substantive democratic principles such as equality and minority protection. What may appear as “anti-system” orientations can thus reflect dissatisfaction with institutional performance rather than rejection of democratic norms. The results presented here are consistent with this interpretation.

A related point concerns the apparent tension between lower abstract support for democracy among the young and their stronger emphasis on specific democratic dimensions. This tension disappears once we distinguish between diffuse regime support and specific normative expectations. Younger Europeans may express weaker attachment to democracy

as an abstract ideal while holding more demanding expectations regarding its substantive content. Lower levels of abstract support should therefore not be interpreted as disengagement, but rather as a shift in how democracy is understood and evaluated.

More broadly, the findings contribute to debates about democratic legitimacy in contemporary Europe. Much of the literature on democratic dissatisfaction emphasizes declining trust in institutions or the rise of populist attitudes. The results presented here suggest a complementary interpretation: **dissatisfaction with democracy often reflects unmet expectations rather than rejection of democratic principles. Citizens may remain strongly committed to democracy while simultaneously expressing dissatisfaction with how democratic systems perform.**

The generational differences identified in this study carry important implications for the future of democratic politics. Younger Europeans do not appear to reject democracy as such, but they evaluate democratic performance through somewhat different normative lenses. Their stronger emphasis on minority rights and redistributive outcomes suggests that the sources of democratic legitimacy may gradually shift as younger cohorts replace older ones – assuming these differences reflect generational rather than purely life-cycle effects. Finally, the findings highlight the importance of addressing expectation–performance gaps in key democratic dimensions. Persistent gaps – particularly in areas such as rule of law, accountability, and social protection – risk undermining democratic satisfaction even in otherwise stable democratic systems. Strengthening the capacity of democratic institutions to understand and meet citizens’ expectations therefore remains a central challenge for European democracies.

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Appendix A

Analyses of variance between and within groups in attitudes towards democracy
ESS 06 (2012) & ESS10 (2022)

ALL AGE GROUPS

Figure A1A. Satisfaction with democracy – 2012

Regions	Summary of How satisfied with the way democracy works in country			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	5.7642676	2.2491903	20,371	14,614
NE	6.9819361	1.8210781	1,640	6,294
SE	4.0228099	2.3882382	9,858	5,946
CEE	4.6674716	2.4296479	6,348	15,090
Total	5.1851343	2.4496137	38,217	41,944

Source	Analysis of variance			F	Prob > F
	SS	df	MS		
Between groups	29794.1281	3	9931.37604	1877.16	0.0000
Within groups	221889.344	41940	5.29063768		
Total	251683.472	41943	6.00060731		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 1.1e+04$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A1B. Satisfaction with democracy – 2022

Regions	Summary of How satisfied with the way democracy works in country			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	5.584593	2.4582858	21,336	17,604
NE	6.8156611	2.265016	1,784	6,115
SE	4.9766046	2.4763997	9,986	7,438
CEE	4.2226226	2.8668793	6,358	14,590
Total	5.2669774	2.5951344	39,464	45,747

Source	Analysis of variance			F	Prob > F
	SS	df	MS		
Between groups	16470.3634	3	5490.12114	861.18	0.0000
Within groups	291616.243	45743	6.37510097		
Total	308086.607	45746	6.73472231		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 6.2e+03$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A2A. Support for democracy (how important) – 2012

Regions	Summary of How important for you to live in democratically governed country			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.5638908	1.9418271	20,646	14,824
NE	9.1940817	1.4459506	1,661	6,378
SE	8.5467134	2.043025	9,956	6,007
CEE	8.1607207	2.2022602	6,460	15,301
Total	8.5192573	2.0060627	38,724	42,510

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	1795.4976	3	598.4992	150.29	0.0000
Within groups	169272.941	42506	3.98233052		
Total	171068.439	42509	4.02428753		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 1.1e+04$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A2B. Support for democracy (how important) – 2022

Regions	Summary of How important for you to live in democratically governed country			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.8116602	1.8899938	21,508	17,740
NE	9.3795444	1.3464079	1,790	6,143
SE	8.7253109	2.0206604	10,032	7,498
CEE	8.5807478	2.1264414	6,402	14,733
Total	8.7782324	1.9489802	39,731	46,114

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	1101.32655	3	367.108848	97.25	0.0000
Within groups	174059.994	46110	3.77488601		
Total	175161.321	46113	3.79852364		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 9.6e+03$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A3A. Normative expectation – national elections are free and fair – 2012

Regions	Summary of National elections are free and fair			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.7912337	1.7285215	20,539	14,734
NE	9.2718884	1.2825681	1,644	6,326
SE	8.9496148	1.6971454	9,842	5,959
CEE	9.0606986	1.6442027	6,463	15,303
Total	8.8975128	1.6947485	38,487	42,322

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	727.067491	3	242.35583	84.88	0.0000
Within groups	120826.14	42318	2.85519496		
Total	121553.208	42321	2.87217239		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 1.3e+04$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A3B. Normative expectation – national elections are free and fair – 2022

Regions	Summary of National elections are free and fair			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.8869299	1.7479515	21,296	17,490
NE	9.3368981	1.3347213	1,785	6,134
SE	8.9351722	1.8135599	10,025	7,516
CEE	9.10392	1.7508463	6,410	14,757
Total	8.9546971	1.752512	39,517	45,897

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	586.740462	3	195.580154	63.94	0.0000
Within groups	140373.566	45893	3.0587141		
Total	140960.307	45896	3.0712983		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 1.0e+04$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A4A. Normative expectation – parties offer clear alternatives – 2012

Regions	Summary of Different political parties offer clear alternatives to one another			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	7.6113216	2.1187432	20,361	14,593
NE	7.9712374	1.8786881	1,633	6,272
SE	8.330987	2.0572442	9,740	5,906
CEE	8.2008771	2.074563	6,279	14,892
Total	7.9085665	2.1115084	38,013	41,663

Source	Analysis of variance			F	Prob > F
	SS	df	MS		
Between groups	4471.71625	3	1490.57208	342.55	0.0000
Within groups	181276.961	41659	4.35144773		
Total	185748.677	41662	4.4584676		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: chi2(3) = **1.1e+04** Prob>chi2 = **0.000**

Figure A4B. Normative expectation – parties offer clear alternatives – 2022

Regions	Summary of Different political parties offer clear alternatives to one another			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	7.7855804	2.1618236	21,080	17,348
NE	8.1368899	1.8137625	1,771	6,079
SE	7.9917741	2.1650789	9,864	7,396
CEE	7.7588081	2.3293745	6,298	14,426
Total	7.8493399	2.1789497	39,013	45,249

Source	Analysis of variance			F	Prob > F
	SS	df	MS		
Between groups	561.210978	3	187.070326	39.50	0.0000
Within groups	214268.222	45245	4.7357326		
Total	214829.433	45248	4.74782162		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: chi2(3) = **7.8e+03** Prob>chi2 = **0.000**

Figure A5A. Normative expectation – free media – 2012

Regions	Summary of The media are free to criticise the government			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	7.8300884	2.3161569	20,559	14,746
NE	8.4349414	1.9405138	1,645	6,327
SE	7.9774764	2.4551492	9,755	5,952
CEE	8.3954267	2.1608258	6,426	15,177
Total	7.9881157	2.3232506	38,385	42,202

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	2098.9491	3	699.6497	130.82	0.0000
Within groups	225680.669	42198	5.34813661		
Total	227779.618	42201	5.39749337		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: chi2(3) = 1.3e+04 Prob>chi2 = 0.000

Figure A5B. Normative expectation – free media – 2022

Regions	Summary of The media are free to criticise the government			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.267041	2.1923125	21,352	17,544
NE	8.7906987	1.8164308	1,785	6,119
SE	8.1925885	2.1010719	9,955	7,471
CEE	8.3876011	2.2247658	6,360	14,673
Total	8.2913787	2.1627781	39,452	45,807

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	712.517946	3	237.505982	50.94	0.0000
Within groups	213550.037	45803	4.66235917		
Total	214262.555	45806	4.67760894		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: chi2(3) = 8.5e+03 Prob>chi2 = 0.000

Figure A6A. Normative expectation – Rights of minorities – 2012

Regions	Summary of The rights of minority groups are protected			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.3817264	1.8834412	20,436	14,659
NE	8.5318545	1.729929	1,637	6,301
SE	8.77233	1.8098141	9,814	5,933
CEE	8.2897019	2.1461511	6,366	15,076
Total	8.473044	1.913885	38,252	41,969

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	1392.3957	3	464.131899	127.86	0.0000
Within groups	152334.531	41965	3.63003767		
Total	153726.927	41968	3.66295574		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 8.3e+03$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A6B. Normative expectation – Rights of minorities – 2022

Regions	Summary of The rights of minority groups are protected			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.3775472	1.9287209	21,226	17,475
NE	8.3569834	1.9773547	1,780	6,116
SE	8.285477	2.0213255	9,982	7,468
CEE	7.7758344	2.4787826	6,355	14,628
Total	8.2560628	2.0636415	39,343	45,687

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	2096.78853	3	698.929509	165.90	0.0000
Within groups	192462.354	45683	4.21299726		
Total	194559.142	45686	4.25861626		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 4.7e+03$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A7A. Normative expectation – Referendums – 2012

Summary of Citizens have the final say on political issues by voting directly in referendum					
Regions	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs	
WE	8.0077754	2.0571952	20,349	14,631	
NE	8.157313	1.8900379	1,632	6,279	
SE	8.6342866	1.8835636	9,697	5,832	
CEE	8.5978356	1.9063842	6,361	15,076	
Total	8.2725728	2.0045465	38,039	41,818	

Analysis of variance					
Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	3726.99455	3	1242.33152	316.17	0.0000
Within groups	164302.35	41814	3.92936219		
Total	168029.345	41817	4.01820659		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: chi2(3) = 1.1e+04 Prob>chi2 = 0.000

Figure A7B. Normative expectation – Referendums – 2022

Summary of Citizens have the final say on political issues by voting directly in referendum					
Regions	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs	
WE	7.5849513	2.3318386	21,125	17,415	
NE	7.6825645	2.1671316	1,774	6,095	
SE	8.1185144	2.0075061	9,906	7,401	
CEE	8.2826903	2.1041972	6,324	14,552	
Total	7.8372267	2.2297161	39,128	45,463	

Analysis of variance					
Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	3980.15899	3	1326.71966	271.62	0.0000
Within groups	222040.259	45459	4.88440702		
Total	226020.418	45462	4.97163385		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: chi2(3) = 8.5e+03 Prob>chi2 = 0.000

Figure A8A. Normative expectation – Rule of law – 2012

Regions	Summary of The courts treat everyone the same			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	9.2158196	1.501086	20,666	14,804
NE	9.5226827	1.1220005	1,649	6,327
SE	9.4251716	1.2974937	9,879	6,017
CEE	9.3282012	1.4871809	6,520	15,372
Total	9.3012402	1.4381936	38,714	42,520

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	426.285957	3	142.095319	69.03	0.0000
Within groups	87520.046	42516	2.05852023		
Total	87946.332	42519	2.06840076		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 1.2e+04$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A8B. Normative expectation – Rule of law – 2022

Regions	Summary of The courts treat everyone the same			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	9.1746162	1.5687505	21,398	17,576
NE	9.3940207	1.3255885	1,785	6,127
SE	9.0315741	1.7143329	10,059	7,544
CEE	9.1247522	1.7409079	6,409	14,784
Total	9.1401431	1.6275931	39,650	46,031

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	302.462766	3	100.820922	38.15	0.0000
Within groups	121633.74	46027	2.64266062		
Total	121936.203	46030	2.64905938		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 8.3e+03$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A9A. Normative expectation – accountability – 2012

Regions	Summary of Governing parties are punished in elections when they have done a bad job			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.3308397	1.945405	20,345	14,604
NE	7.9892671	2.1780729	1,605	6,189
SE	8.9637877	1.7580399	9,789	5,906
CEE	8.6646721	1.9085236	6,345	14,968
Total	8.5347562	1.9255162	38,084	41,667

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	3536.67222	3	1178.89074	325.39	0.0000
Within groups	150944.72	41663	3.62299211		
Total	154481.393	41666	3.70761275		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 8.2e+03$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A9B. Normative expectation – accountability – 2022

Regions	Summary of Governing parties are punished in elections when they have done a bad job			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.0317364	2.1162936	20,995	17,265
NE	7.6865591	2.3285861	1,756	6,015
SE	8.6095645	1.9062866	9,944	7,461
CEE	8.594941	2.05796	6,335	14,554
Total	8.2548399	2.0876487	39,030	45,295

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	4173.367	3	1391.12233	326.06	0.0000
Within groups	193230.427	45291	4.26641997		
Total	197403.794	45294	4.3582769		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 6.3e+03$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A10A. Normative expectation – protect against poverty – 2012

Regions	Summary of The government protects all citizens against poverty			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.5523074	1.8888124	20,596	14,800
NE	8.5385127	1.7874998	1,643	6,309
SE	9.2714848	1.4432049	9,932	6,028
CEE	8.7478518	2.0089533	6,521	15,360
Total	8.7692913	1.8279831	38,692	42,497

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	3915.64881	3	1305.21627	401.65	0.0000
Within groups	138085.674	42493	3.24960991		
Total	142001.323	42496	3.34152209		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 7.8e+03$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A10B. Normative expectation – protect against poverty – 2022

Regions	Summary of The government protects all citizens against poverty			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.4797905	1.9457056	21,440	17,590
NE	8.2742343	1.97635	1,783	6,116
SE	8.5886104	1.9129153	10,059	7,545
CEE	8.1946709	2.2731353	6,401	14,749
Total	8.4521465	1.9997321	39,684	46,000

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	793.459083	3	264.486361	66.42	0.0000
Within groups	183153.247	45996	3.98193858		
Total	183946.706	45999	3.99892837		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 5.2e+03$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A11B. Normative expectation – redistribution – 2012

Regions	Summary of The government takes measures to reduce differences in income levels			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	7.7803598	2.2632511	20,483	14,705
NE	8.0622372	2.0232458	1,635	6,280
SE	8.8912	1.7222714	9,825	5,951
CEE	8.4526286	2.2188019	6,458	15,256
Total	8.1896312	2.1727103	38,401	42,192

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	9603.06497	3	3201.02166	712.39	0.0000
Within groups	189566.725	42188	4.49338022		
Total	199169.79	42191	4.72067004		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: chi2(3) = 9.5e+03 Prob>chi2 = 0.000

Figure A11B. Normative expectation – redistribution – 2022

Regions	Summary of The government takes measures to reduce differences in income levels			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	7.6641733	2.3224001	21,309	17,496
NE	7.3138263	2.4359187	1,776	6,100
SE	7.9128119	2.2726569	10,021	7,511
CEE	7.3641563	2.7891578	6,352	14,680
Total	7.6632545	2.4040047	39,458	45,787

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	1635.25914	3	545.086379	94.90	0.0000
Within groups	262972.967	45783	5.74389986		
Total	264608.226	45786	5.77923877		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: chi2(3) = 4.6e+03 Prob>chi2 = 0.000

YOUNG = 18-34

Figure A13A. Satisfaction with democracy – 2012

Regions	Summary of How satisfied with the way democracy works in country			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	5.8706925	2.2797977	2,160	1,211
NE	7.1075417	1.8089436	180	636
SE	4.0618113	2.2071754	958	510
CEE	5.0614575	2.2372259	719	1,285
Total	5.3497617	2.3853681	4,018	3,642

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	2530.68122	3	843.560407	168.74	0.0000
Within groups	18186.5395	3638	4.99904879		
Total	20717.2207	3641	5.68998097		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: chi2(3) = 1.1e+03 Prob>chi2 = 0.000

Figure A13B. Satisfaction with democracy – 2022

Regions	Summary of How satisfied with the way democracy works in country			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	5.6577803	2.2867106	2,173	1,474
NE	6.9929877	2.0498335	178	477
SE	4.9246575	2.4065393	997	594
CEE	4.3235089	2.611035	643	1,144
Total	5.3194533	2.4415892	3,991	3,689

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	1424.16456	3	474.72152	85.08	0.0000
Within groups	20561.3229	3685	5.57973484		
Total	21985.4874	3688	5.96135777		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: chi2(3) = 518.0834 Prob>chi2 = 0.000

Figure A14A. Support for democracy – 2012

Regions	Summary of How important for you to live in democratically governed country			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.2898699	2.0154052	2,186	1,229
NE	8.8552342	1.6587902	183	648
SE	8.3029749	2.0449123	964	511
CEE	7.9973892	2.1417336	732	1,309
Total	8.2657399	2.0375818	4,065	3,697

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	108.167803	3	36.0559343	8.74	0.0000
Within groups	15236.6623	3693	4.12582244		
Total	15344.8301	3696	4.15173974		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 1.0e+03$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A14B. Support for democracy – 2022

Regions	Summary of How important for you to live in democratically governed country			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.543988	1.9909962	2,202	1,480
NE	9.1869829	1.5354706	178	481
SE	8.2943735	2.2674417	999	598
CEE	8.1825356	2.3336374	651	1,164
Total	8.4521766	2.1135914	4,031	3,723

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	172.865704	3	57.6219012	13.02	0.0000
Within groups	16454.3084	3719	4.42439053		
Total	16627.1741	3722	4.4672687		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 685.7616$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A15A. Normative expectation – national elections are free and fair – 2022

Regions	Summary of National elections are free and fair			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.6323933	1.6998655	2,192	1,231
NE	8.9154518	1.5788262	181	643
SE	8.7552566	1.7101638	956	509
CEE	8.8888831	1.7559084	733	1,316
Total	8.7201898	1.7099438	4,062	3,699

Source	Analysis of variance			F	Prob > F
	SS	df	MS		
Between groups	41.727863	3	13.9092877	4.77	0.0025
Within groups	10770.8834	3695	2.91498874		
Total	10812.6112	3698	2.92390785		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 935.1107$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A15B. Normative expectation – national elections are free and fair – 2022

Regions	Summary of National elections are free and fair			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.8124022	1.7206111	2,191	1,472
NE	9.1054964	1.5976038	179	483
SE	8.812858	1.9528102	995	594
CEE	8.8587828	1.922564	648	1,163
Total	8.8330546	1.8093985	4,013	3,712

Source	Analysis of variance			F	Prob > F
	SS	df	MS		
Between groups	13.8990595	3	4.63301984	1.42	0.2362
Within groups	12135.6284	3708	3.2728232		
Total	12149.5275	3711	3.27392279		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 591.4604$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A16A. Normative expectation – parties offer clear alternatives – 2012

Regions	Summary of Different political parties offer clear alternatives to one another			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	7.5902336	1.9343148	2,170	1,216
NE	7.7729874	1.9399517	180	639
SE	8.2088806	1.8508906	954	510
CEE	8.0645143	2.0332751	714	1,273
Total	7.8296142	1.9517402	4,018	3,638

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	273.070832	3	91.0236106	24.36	0.0000
Within groups	13581.3163	3634	3.73729122		
Total	13854.3871	3637	3.80928984		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 792.8029$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A16B. Normative expectation – parties offer clear alternatives – 2022

Regions	Summary of Different political parties offer clear alternatives to one another			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	7.6752502	1.9972993	2,178	1,458
NE	8.0890278	1.8113297	176	476
SE	7.916403	2.0403944	977	586
CEE	7.4665039	2.3248516	633	1,128
Total	7.7196891	2.061704	3,964	3,648

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	98.2055074	3	32.7351691	7.74	0.0000
Within groups	15403.8176	3644	4.22717278		
Total	15502.0231	3647	4.25062328		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 478.5854$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A17A. Normative expectation – free media – 2012

Regions	Summary of The media are free to criticise the government			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	7.5390929	2.3454969	2,190	1,237
NE	7.9602605	2.1273862	182	645
SE	7.5271288	2.3291021	957	511
CEE	8.0643874	2.3533755	727	1,297
Total	7.649257	2.3424372	4,055	3,690

Source	Analysis of variance			F	Prob > F
	SS	df	MS		
Between groups	167.106547	3	55.7021825	10.23	0.0000
Within groups	20074.4812	3686	5.4461425		
Total	20241.5878	3689	5.48701214		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 975.5587$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A17B. Normative expectation – free media – 2022

Regions	Summary of The media are free to criticise the government			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.1868585	2.1451132	2,196	1,471
NE	8.6268464	1.9082168	177	478
SE	7.9701671	2.1801332	994	595
CEE	8.2530833	2.2141435	639	1,149
Total	8.1631294	2.1590527	4,007	3,693

Source	Analysis of variance			F	Prob > F
	SS	df	MS		
Between groups	75.1586023	3	25.0528674	5.39	0.0011
Within groups	17135.1309	3689	4.64492569		
Total	17210.2895	3692	4.66150852		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 607.1385$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A18A. Normative expectation – Rights of minorities – 2012

Regions	Summary of The rights of minority groups are protected			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.2818926	1.7989851	2,168	1,226
NE	8.4363925	1.7660717	181	644
SE	8.6048521	1.8262039	943	504
CEE	8.2308865	2.2468053	725	1,291
Total	8.3554548	1.8970388	4,016	3,665

Source	Analysis of variance			F	Prob > F
	SS	df	MS		
Between groups	75.5472441	3	25.1824147	7.03	0.0001
Within groups	13110.2952	3661	3.58106943		
Total	13185.8424	3664	3.59875612		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 687.7871$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A18B. Normative expectation – Rights of minorities – 2022

Regions	Summary of The rights of minority groups are protected			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.4643793	1.880414	2,190	1,466
NE	8.6453192	1.7886485	176	478
SE	8.419554	1.9788649	986	589
CEE	7.747382	2.4472798	643	1,152
Total	8.3459573	2.019194	3,995	3,685

Source	Analysis of variance			F	Prob > F
	SS	df	MS		
Between groups	260.258528	3	86.7528425	21.64	0.0000
Within groups	14759.9417	3681	4.0097641		
Total	15020.2002	3684	4.07714446		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 397.3486$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A19A. Normative expectation – Referendums – 2012

Summary of Citizens have the final say on political issues by voting directly in referendum					
Regions	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs	
WE	7.9085335	1.9307883	2,165	1,217	
NE	8.2972756	1.8083742	179	635	
SE	8.5020587	1.8602146	923	498	
CEE	8.4809383	1.9101698	713	1,280	
Total	8.1661718	1.9258633	3,980	3,630	

Analysis of variance					
Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	293.285704	3	97.7619014	26.92	0.0000
Within groups	13166.4924	3626	3.63113413		
Total	13459.7781	3629	3.70894959		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 929.9964$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A19B. Normative expectation – Referendums – 2022

Summary of Citizens have the final say on political issues by voting directly in referendum					
Regions	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs	
WE	7.659691	2.1413507	2,171	1,470	
NE	7.6265652	2.1691224	177	474	
SE	8.0220734	2.0784747	990	591	
CEE	7.9455207	2.1910563	639	1,144	
Total	7.79435	2.1409334	3,977	3,679	

Analysis of variance					
Source	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	102.024099	3	34.0080329	7.46	0.0001
Within groups	16756.441	3675	4.55957579		
Total	16858.4651	3678	4.58359574		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 490.7106$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A20A. Normative expectation – Rule of law – 2012

Regions	Summary of The courts treat everyone the same			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	9.0360636	1.6396142	2,215	1,251
NE	9.4412975	1.2717199	182	645
SE	9.3172522	1.2275108	953	515
CEE	9.1501491	1.6548442	740	1,318
Total	9.1402723	1.5459369	4,090	3,729

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	64.2385112	3	21.4128371	9.02	0.0000
Within groups	8845.38621	3725	2.37460032		
Total	8909.62472	3728	2.38992079		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 1.0e+03$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A20B. Normative expectation – Rule of law – 2022

Regions	Summary of The courts treat everyone the same			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	9.1163247	1.5440381	2,191	1,475
NE	9.2983919	1.4420318	177	477
SE	8.8692214	1.9370977	1,004	597
CEE	8.8346115	1.9634918	650	1,167
Total	9.0170796	1.7226338	4,022	3,716

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	73.1391888	3	24.3797296	8.26	0.0000
Within groups	10951.0021	3712	2.95016219		
Total	11024.1412	3715	2.96746736		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 580.0880$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A21A. Normative expectation – accountability – 2012

Regions	Summary of Governing parties are punished in elections when they have done a bad job			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	7.783546	2.0168093	2,169	1,220
NE	7.7447088	2.1525415	175	623
SE	8.5920752	1.8668687	935	504
CEE	8.341311	2.072776	718	1,285
Total	8.0712352	2.029813	3,998	3,632

Source	Analysis of variance			F	Prob > F
	SS	df	MS		
Between groups	458.173056	3	152.724352	38.21	0.0000
Within groups	14502.0581	3628	3.99725967		
Total	14960.2311	3631	4.12014077		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 734.2437$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A21B. Normative expectation – accountability – 2022

Regions	Summary of Governing parties are punished in elections when they have done a bad job			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	7.4200522	2.2553794	2,129	1,428
NE	7.4014318	2.4840398	174	463
SE	8.199627	2.1546342	990	592
CEE	8.2018471	2.2828795	638	1,141
Total	7.7424905	2.277609	3,931	3,624

Source	Analysis of variance			F	Prob > F
	SS	df	MS		
Between groups	537.57314	3	179.191047	35.53	0.0000
Within groups	18256.7494	3620	5.04330093		
Total	18794.3225	3623	5.18750277		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 441.8296$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A22A. Normative expectation – protect against poverty – 2012

Regions	Summary of The government protects all citizens against poverty			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.3549597	1.9454318	2,206	1,245
NE	8.4401174	2.0213962	181	644
SE	9.0528534	1.4354585	955	514
CEE	8.3944533	2.2488022	740	1,323
Total	8.5291903	1.9253466	4,082	3,726

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	313.753597	3	104.584532	28.85	0.0000
Within groups	13494.6705	3722	3.62565032		
Total	13808.4241	3725	3.70695949		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 612.7872$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A22B. Normative expectation – protect against poverty – 2022

Regions	Summary of The government protects all citizens against poverty			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	8.412679	1.9499782	2,212	1,484
NE	8.1758789	2.162278	178	478
SE	8.5176759	2.0345623	1,010	601
CEE	7.6235385	2.5678215	648	1,161
Total	8.3022119	2.1120911	4,048	3,724

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	345.089183	3	115.029728	26.31	0.0000
Within groups	16262.9494	3720	4.37176058		
Total	16608.0386	3723	4.46092897		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 286.4892$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A23A. Normative expectation – redistribution – 2012

Regions	Summary of The government takes measures to reduce differences in income levels			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	7.5281483	2.1817759	2,196	1,239
NE	7.736468	2.0738663	180	638
SE	8.6606411	1.668999	945	509
CEE	8.0244921	2.5192024	730	1,308
Total	7.8911284	2.1852756	4,051	3,694

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	790.096446	3	263.365482	57.69	0.000
Within groups	16845.5645	3690	4.56519363		
Total	17635.6609	3693	4.77542944		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 693.3773$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$

Figure A23B. Normative expectation – redistribution – 2022

Regions	Summary of The government takes measures to reduce differences in income levels			
	Mean	Std. dev.	Freq.	Obs
WE	7.6266529	2.2433255	2,192	1,468
NE	7.0171455	2.5996087	175	472
SE	7.700499	2.2651482	1,008	599
CEE	6.491033	3.0781425	639	1,150
Total	7.4377672	2.4541474	4,014	3,689

Source	Analysis of variance				
	SS	df	MS	F	Prob > F
Between groups	690.813305	3	230.271102	39.43	0.000
Within groups	21521.4194	3685	5.84027663		
Total	22212.2327	3688	6.02283966		

Bartlett's equal-variances test: $\chi^2(3) = 224.8838$ Prob> $\chi^2 = 0.000$